

Formidlingsaktivitet

Art: FysikLab / STEM projekt-baseret læring & didaktik

Sted: SDU / FysikLab.

Skole: Kolding Gymnasium.

Dato: 04. Februar 2026.

Tid: 10:00 – 13:00.

Antal deltagere: 60.

GDPR / pictures for public? Yes. Permission obtained.

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Formidler: Tobias Cornelius Hinse (FKF/SDU-Galaxy).

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